

GENETIC DIVERGENCE IN FORAGE MAIZE (*ZEA MAYS* L.)

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SUMMARY Based on nonhierarchical Euclidean cluster analysis, 100 forage maize accessions and a known forage maize variety African Tall were grouped into eight clusters for fodder as well as kernel yielding traits, in combined form based on 20 metric traits. Cluster III composed of 26 accessions was the largest group with average response of each trait and cluster IV was monogenotypic with high yield. Wide range of means was observed for all the traits. The maximum intercluster distance was observed between cluster IV and V. Cluster IV was more divergent than the other clusters. The study showed that the cross between cluster IV and II with high and low cluster means for majority of characters will help to improve fodder and kernel yield as well as quality in forage maize.

Keywords: Forage maize, genetic divergence, variability, kernel, *Zea mays*.

INTRODUCTION

The diversity and utility of forage maize has been a subject of appreciation since long. Maize stands out as one of the most important cereal crops in the world with enormous role in food, fodder and nutritional security. From tassel to root, the maize plant is valuable. The stem, leaves, silk cob and kernels all have a commercial value. The use of maize as an animal feed is well known. It is the cheapest and most palatable carbonaceous for animals such as cattle, sheep, pig and poultry. It forms an excellent forage and better than all other forage crops in average yield of dry matter and digestible nutrients per hectare (Perry 1988). Being a C₄ plant it has very high production potential. Most of the maize crop is fed to livestock as grain, silage or fodder. Forage maize

leaves are particularly high in crude protein (11%) and rich in calcium and phosphorus for high milk yield. Forage maize plant does not have problems of prussic acid or hydrocyanic acid and therefore, it can be used as fodder even before flowering or in dry weather. Quite often maize crop is grown for a dual purpose for both fodder and grain. The diversity of environment under which maize is grown is unmatched by any other crop. The future of forage maize depends on the careful screening of the genotypes from the germplasm collection. Singh et al. (2005) have made core collections of forage maize from different geographical regions of India through many exploration programs and these accessions were preserved in National Gene Bank (National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources, New Delhi).

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The accessions were evaluated and grouped for various fodder and kernel traits.

In view of the above, present study on the evaluation of accessions of forage maize, which is used as dual purpose crop in India was taken up. Genetic divergence is an essential requirement for any crop improvement programme because genetically diverse parents when crossed can bring together diversity of gene combinations either to exploit heterosis or to obtain superior recombinants. In maize, it is well known that adequate genetic diversity is necessary in breeding programme for development of high yielding varieties. Multivariate analysis is a useful tool for quantifying the degree of divergence between biological population at accession level and assessing relative contribution of different components to the total divergence at both inter- and intracluster levels (Murty & Arunachalam 1966). Therefore, an attempt has been made to evaluate the magnitude of genetic divergence among 101 accessions of forage maize including African Tall.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials for the present study comprised of 100 accessions of forage maize collected from different parts of India mainly Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan and Uttar Pradesh. The accessions were evaluated with known forage maize variety namely, African Tall in randomised block design with three replications for three consecutive years, 2001–2003. Each accession was evaluated in a plot of two rows of 4 M length at 0.4 M apart. In order to maintain the genetic purity and to avoid cross pollination, selected plants were bagged till pollination was over. Observations were recorded on 20 metric traits at 50% silking stage and at the maturity of the crop. Crude

protein content was determined by the conventional Kjeldal method. The metric traits data were analysed statistically using non-hierarchical Euclidean cluster analysis of grouping of genotypes proposed by Spark (1973). The replicated data were averaged over replicates and then cluster analysis was performed.

OBSERVATIONS

Means and genetic variance

The analysis of variance showed a wide range of variation and significant differences for all the traits. Estimation of the different quantitative parameters for fodder and kernel yield and their component characters over environments showed that amongst fodder, green fodder yield itself was highly variable. Similarly, the kernel yield per plant also exhibited maximum variation amongst the accessions followed by its contributing traits like number of kernels per row, thereby indicating the accessions under study were relatively more variable for these characters and provide an opportunity for selection. On the other hand crude protein content in leaf, stem and cob width showed low variation over the environment.

Genetic divergence

Based on nonhierarchical Euclidean cluster analysis the 101 accessions including African Tall were grouped into eight clusters, each having 15, 12, 26, 1, 2, 16, 19 and 10 accessions respectively (Table 1). The composition of clusters showed that accessions of a cluster originate from a wide range of ecogeographical areas, thereby suggested that genetic differences and similarities among the accessions were irrespective of the areas. This allows us to select parents for hybridization on the basis of genetic diversity and not merely on the basis of ecogeographical isolation.

TABLE 1: Composition of clusters for various fodder and seed yield characters in forage maize over three environments.

Cluster No.	Number of accessions	Accession number/ name
I	15	IC - 334821, 334889, 334904, 334920, 334947, 334989, 335051, 335056, 335062, 335069, 335079, 335082, 335086, 335144 and 335169.
II	12	IC - 334830, 334833, 334834, 334837, 334846, 334855, 334872, 334879, 334881, 334915, 334945 and 334949.
III	26	IC - 334826, 334955, 334973, 335028, 335045, 335053, 335089, 335098, 335103, 335109, 335110, 335111, 335112, 335115, 335120, 335128, 335131, 335138, 335141, 335149, 335156, 335158, 335164, 335173, 335178 and 335184.
IV	1	African Tall
V	2	IC - 335060, 335068.
VI	16	IC - 334836, 334838, 334841, 334853, 334863, 334864, 334867, 334869, 334871, 334876, 334877, 334880, 334884, 334943, 334954 and 334957.
VII	19	IC - 334825, 334974, 334996, 334999, 335000, 335009, 335017, 335024, 335025, 335043, 335048, 335050, 335092, 335094, 335116, 335117, 335122, 335128 and 335152.
VIII	10	IC - 334842, 334848, 334929, 334932, 334942, 334944, 335027, 335032, 335035 and 335041.

TABLE 2: Distance between cluster centroids among eight clusters of forage maize.

Cluster No.	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII
I	0.000							
II	6.098	0.000						
III	3.007	4.716	0.000					
IV	17.443	13.167	15.261	0.000				
V	4.739	10.302	7.322	20.971	0.000			
VI	5.508	3.176	4.490	13.357	9.349	0.000		
VII	4.589	5.437	2.824	14.227	8.402	4.094	0.000	
VIII	5.231	4.474	4.065	12.951	8.853	3.168	3.156	0.000

Cluster grouping

The average intercluster distance was zero for all possible pairs of combinations (Table 2). The average intercluster distance values ranged from 2.82 to 20.97. For all the traits, maximum intercluster distance was observed between cluster IV and V (20.97) followed by I to IV (17.44), III to IV (15.26), IV to VII (14.22), IV to VI (13.35) and II to IV (13.16). Cluster IV was more divergent to each cluster. The distribution pattern of clustering reveals considerable diversity among the accessions.

Cluster mean

The diversity in the present material was also supported by the appreciable amount of variation among cluster mean for different traits. The genetic lines belonging to cluster IV were performing better results for all the traits including dry fodder yield and kernel yield under study except leaf-stem ratio.

Being a cereal crop, forage maize is not rich in protein content (leaf + stem) however, cluster I had highest value percentile for crude protein. Therefore, this group will help in improving protein content in forage maize. Days to 50% silking and maturity were found early for cluster V having only two accessions explored from Hardoi district, Uttar Pradesh were showing lowest values for almost all the traits except leaf-stem ratio and number of kernel rows which were showing highest value (Table 3).

Late maturity promoted cob length, cob width, number of kernels per row, shank diameter, kernel length, kernel width and test weight which were recorded in cluster IV. Minimum values of cluster mean for cob width, number of kernels per row and shank diameter was found in cluster II. Kernel width was highest for cluster IV and lower for cluster I.

TABLE 3: Cluster means for different fodder and seed yield characters in forage maize.

Clusters	Days to 50% silking	Plant height (cm)	No. of leaves/plant	Leaf blade length (cm)	Sheath length (cm)	Leaf width (cm)	Stem girth (cm)	Dry Fodder yield/plant (g)	Leaf-Stem ratio	Crude Protein (%)	Days to maturity	Cob length (cm)	Cob width (cm)	No. of kernel rows	Kernels /row	Shank diameter (cm)	Kernel length (cm)	Kernel width (cm)	Test weight (g)	Seed yield/plant (g)
I	45.87	169.49	11.06	80.68	15.52	7.71	1.88	75.50	0.42	11.12	78.44	14.64	3.43	12.76	29.05	1.18	0.81	0.80	18.17	165.54
II	51.18	207.82	12.67	93.82	18.30	9.05	2.20	110.87	0.38	10.53	88.48	13.76	3.36	11.76	25.30	1.14	0.86	0.82	20.12	158.87
III	46.11	188.00	11.58	86.72	16.72	8.32	1.99	89.21	0.40	10.60	77.45	16.51	3.36	12.23	33.88	1.26	0.83	0.81	18.16	178.75
IV	59.22	268.93	17.44	104.81	20.54	10.21	2.94	170.29	0.47	8.66	119.33	21.34	3.71	13.17	39.26	1.62	0.94	0.90	25.73	261.61
V	45.11	152.87	10.04	69.30	13.55	6.96	1.54	44.74	0.54	11.10	73.00	12.76	3.51	13.91	26.67	1.22	0.83	0.78	17.09	165.17
VI	51.44	195.35	12.54	87.90	17.21	8.54	2.15	94.05	0.40	10.78	87.46	15.05	3.50	11.63	26.14	1.19	0.92	0.89	22.52	186.52
VII	45.80	190.58	11.65	87.60	16.47	8.22	2.03	99.26	0.35	10.78	78.11	16.99	3.60	12.41	33.95	1.38	0.88	0.86	20.72	214.61
VIII	49.94	196.18	12.81	85.11	16.93	8.78	2.14	100.63	0.40	10.93	84.32	16.41	3.69	13.48	31.68	1.26	0.93	0.83	21.32	194.42

DISCUSSION

The analysis of variance estimation for the accessions showed relatively high variations in the characters and provides good opportunity for their selection (Ertiro et al. 2013). Murty & Arunachalam (1966) reported that the genetic diversity among the genetic lines of common geographic origin could be due to factors like heterogeneity, genetic architecture of the population, past history of selection and developmental traits. The use of accessions in hybridization from these cluster groups having most of the desirable characters is likely to produce more transgressive segregants (Alom et al. 2003, Kant et al. 2001, Katiyar et al. 2000). Gupta et al. (1984) have recommended that fodder variety should be early growth and late flowering type while Srivas & Singh (2004) concluded that the improvement in characters like plant height, days to 50% silking, number of leaves per plant and stem girth will help to improve the fodder yield in maize both directly and indirectly. Clustering pattern could be utilized in choosing parents for cross combinations which may likely generate exploitable variability for the effective selection of various economic traits (Endang et al. 1971). As per earlier reports heterosis and better recombinants can be obtained by crossing between parents of clusters of high and low means (Usha Kumari et al. 2010). Therefore, for getting better heterosis the genetic lines from cluster IV and II with high and low cluster means for majority of characters respectively can be used for hybridization programme for improvement of yield in fodder and/or kernel in forage maize.

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